

Determinants of Debt Maturity in Non-Financial Firms (Pakistan Stock Exchange)

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Abstract

The paper has examined the determinants of debt maturity structure. The study has been carried out in the non-financial firms in Pakistan Stock Exchange. The study has collected data for listed 224 firms from 2010 to 2019. The study has used different models to estimate different determinants of debt maturity. The findings reveal that the agency cost hypotheses has been supported by the existing results. The firms always match the assets maturity with their debt maturity which saves them from the liquidity risk and also from future financial issues. The matching of assets and debts controls the agency problem and also the conflict among the firm and creditors. The tax hypotheses argued that the higher tax rate in the market will lead to have higher usage of debt instruments. The result shows that there is a negative relationship with the firm quality and debt maturity. The finding recommends that the non-financial firms in Pakistan will prefer to use debts as compared to equity due to the tax yield. The firms are trying to increase their assets as they will give them more shields to complete their claims in future.

Keywords: Debt maturity, assets quality, firm size, non-financial, OLS, GMM etc

1. Introduction

In corporate finance, the financial decisions of the company are not only related to their profitability but it is also linked with the indebtedness of the firm. The researchers suggested that the financial experts should take full care while selecting the debts instruments for the firm. The important aspect while considering the debt instruments is its maturity. The finance managers should examined maturity period and develop their activity while selecting debt instruments. The trend of studying debt maturities has been starts in 50s after the milestone of Modigliani and Miller (1958) and they introduce several theories related to the numerous financial phenomena. As per these theories, different studies have been conducted and as a result multiple hypotheses have been introduced for the debt determinants and debt choices for the firms. These studies have concluded different factors which can be associated with debt maturity i.e. bankruptcy, agency cost, growth opportunities, asymmetry of information and taxation policy.

After some time, the researchers show a greater interest in examining the concept of debt maturity, they conducted multiple studies and concluded with different findings dependent on their capital markets. In this connection, the study of Merton (1974) suggested that in perfect capital markets, the debt maturity shows irrelevance to the firm value. This means that the usage of both short and longer debt instruments can be seem effective in imperfect market conditions. The studies exhibits that the badly chosen of the debt maturity will leads to have liquidity problems and then might affect the positive NPV of the projects. In imperfect market, the choices of debt maturity pass signals to the market regarding their credibility, quality and future prospect. Signaling model states that the over or under valued firms uses longer/shorter debts passes signals to the market for the under or over valuation. Fama (1990) suggested that the firm's debt maturity structure shows the firm financial approach, monitoring and bonding relevant for contracts.

The strand of theories related to the debt maturity is based on the taxation argument. The study of Brick and Ravid (1985) states that when the interest rate is getting higher boom then the long term debts instruments might be appreciate as the interest tax shield saving from leverage is accelerated (incentives for borrowers) and interest income is delayed (incentive for lenders). The study further added that when even when the interest rate is moving down or uncertain then in the same case the long term debt will be prefer. The study of Stohs and

Mauer (1996) found that the tax factor is associated with the choices of debt instrument while Guedes and Opler (1996) do not agree with taxation effect. The second strand in this regard is related to the information asymmetry. Flannery (1986) contended that shorter debt instruments might be feasible for the larger firms as they pass signal to the market for their type. The findings have been supported by Stohs and Mauer (1996). The study of Diamond (1991) argued that even in the case of low quality firms will prefer to have shorter debt instruments to handle the liquidity risk and only medium level firms will use longer debt instruments. The same findings have been empirically supported by Barclay and Smith (1995).

The next important strand is the costs argument related to the debt maturity. According to Myers (1977) states that short term debt instrument shows the firm's under investment issues in case when the debts mature before the growth, as these debts instruments have investment opportunities for lender of re-contract. The findings of Barnea et al., (1980) argued that the short term debts can be used as assets substitute due to the issue that the short term debts are found less sensitive to the assets value of the firm. Some of the studies have supported the empirical findings but majority of the while some of them rejected the assumption and impact of short term debts. Looking at the importance of information asymmetry, the firm are always interested in matching the maturity of debts and assets (Hart and Moore, 1994).

This study explored the determinants of debt maturity by considering different cost factors and it are contributing in the literature in different ways. The study has examined the cost factor, taxes, maturing, liquidity and signaling factors. A few studies in Pakistani have been conducted by analyzing the endogeneity problem by GMM (Generalized Method of Moments). The model has been found significant in random shocks for dependent and independent variables at the same time. The issue of endogeneity has been controlled by GMM model and that is the reason for the selection. The model has been found significant in controlling the issue of normality, heteroscedasticity etc.

2. Literature Review

Different studies conducted on the numerous factors affecting the debt maturity of the firm and its role in their value, emerged after the pioneer study of Modigliani and Miller (1958). Different studies came up with different findings on the basis of their markets and this was taken as the theme of the existing literature.

Modigliani and Miller (1958) were the first who argued that the different factors i.e. taxes linked with the firm financing mix does not have any significant effect on the firm value. after this, several authors have conducted their study but were not found agreed to the statements and examination for the determinants of debt maturity has been started from a decades. The statements of the above studies have been associated to the decisions of capital structure as well. However, both the concepts are equally important and significant for the firm's financial decisions and this is not only restricted to the debt maturity. Thus, the important point is to analyze the important financial theories which can be considered for the decision making of financing choice.

After several studies conducted on the above concept, the agency theory has been emerged and especially the studies of Wilson (1968) and Arrow (1971) who examined the concept of risk sharing among the individuals and different groups especially when different stakeholders have different attitude towards risk. The studies conducted by Jensen and Meckling (1976) and Ross (1973) argued that the agency theory is related to this issue especially and having goals to control the conflicts among the creditors and shareholders of the firm. These studies argued that the agency theory is related to the debt maturity of the firm and this has been found reflective for the level of conflicts among the managers and shareholders and linked with the firm size, risk shifting and issues of under investment.

Krishnaswami et al., (1999) larger firms which has been financed majority from the debts level which will be exposed more to the risk as compared to the smaller firms having low ratio of debts in their financing mix. The bigger firms can manage such kind of issue and can get economies of scale by issuing different public

securities, as per the findings of Colla et al., (2013), Johnson (1997) & Houston and James (1996) are in favoring of issuing private and public securities to cover the risk associated to the debt financing. The larger firms prefer the public debts to cover the issue of risk associated to the debt and this is due to the significance of having lower rates attached with the public securities in the market (Carey et al., 1993). Following this concept, the firm with larger portion of debt financing for the firm will prefer to issue private and public debt securities as they can be used to control the risk associated.

The study of Ozkan (2000) states that the bigger firms will have low agency cost as they can have significantly approach the stock market and can efficiently using the securities, managing the size of the firm and they can manage the risk attached which can be treated as the important factors of agency problem. The smaller firms are having limited access to the stock market for the long term debt securities which means that they will have low ratio of marketable assets and they can have negative impact on the growth of the firm (Whited, 1992). The study conducted by Yi (2005) argued that the smaller firms will have more investment and growth opportunities as they have smaller size, agency cost argued that the risk is attached with the risky business will have benefit of lower agency cost by having lower debt maturity.

3. Data & Methods

3.1.Data

The data in the existing study has been collected from the “Balance Sheet Analysis of non-Financial Firms” issued by Pakistan Stock Exchange. Other official annual reports of sample can also be taken as the source of data collection. the data for the sample has been collected from 2010 to 2019 for only those firms who have listed in the stock market on September 1st 2020.

3.2. Analysis

For the data analysis, ten years data have been collected from annual reports and reports of SBP Statistics department. The study has included only those firms have no negative equity observation in the sample time period. The firms having negative equity have been excluded from the data sheet for the analysis. As the negative equity reflects that the debt maturity and capital structure decisions for the firm is facing constraints. Those firms who accumulated loss for the selected 10 years have also been excluded. After following stated criteria, the study came up with selected 224 non-financial firms and they have been included in the data analysis.

3.3. Variables

Debt Maturity (Dependent)

The debt maturity in the study has been taken as the dependent variable. Different studies have been used different proxies for the debt maturity i.e. some of the studies have used ratio of long term liabilities (5 years) to short term liabilities (1 years) Ozkan (2000). While some of the studies have used ratio of debt maturing more than 3 years to total debts (Varouj et al., 2005) and some have taken debt maturing than 1 year to total debts (Shah and Khan, 2009). The study will adopt the proxy of Shah and Khan (2009):

$$DM = \frac{\text{Debt maturing in more than 1 year}}{\text{total debts}}$$

3.4. Independent

Asset Maturity

When the firm is having higher assets maturity as compared to their debt maturity, then they will face the cash flow problem as the cash flow will not be appropriate to manage their obligations (Stohs and Mauer, 1996). If the firm is financing their short term assets with longer debt maturity then the funds will be not activity using in project and they will be used in low activities (Shah & Khan, 2009). The statement shows a positive relationship with of assets maturity with the debt maturity. The existing study has adopted Oppcycle which is the ratio of net sales to net fixed assets adopted from Shah and Khan, (2009).

$$AM = \frac{Net\ sales}{Net\ fixed\ assets}$$

Firm Quality

Firm quality has been taken as independent variable by following Shah and Khan, (2009). The study argued that information asymmetry always exists between investors and management and to manage this issue, the firm always issue short term debts to reduce the cost of information asymmetry, in this case the firm will issue short term debts (Flannery, 1996). This shows a negative relationship between firm quality and debt maturity (Barclay and Smith, 1995). The study has taken firm's abnormal profit as a proxy of firm quality:

$$FQ = \frac{Earning\ t+1 - Earning\ t}{Earning\ t}$$

Tax Rate

Tax rate in the existing study was taken as independent variable. Different studies have conducted on the taxation and debt maturity and they states debt maturity decrease with tax shield. The model developed by Kane et al., (1985) argued that the firm always use the tradeoff of long term and short term debt instruments by assuming some factors, taxation is one of them. The existing study has used:

$$TR = \frac{Annual\ tax\ expense}{Taxable\ Income}$$

Model Specification (GMM)

Studies argued that the concept of debt maturity is the selection among the two options of financing. Different companies have taken different options dependent on the different factors which can give higher benefits to the firm. In debt maturity, the firm has only two options i.e. shorter debt instruments and long term debts. When the firm instantly switches to the options and there is not switching costs, then the recommended model will be the statistic model. If the firm is taking time for the selection of any suitable options then statistic model will not be appropriate (Shah and Khan, 2009; Ozkan, 2000).

$$DM_{it} = \alpha DM_{i,t-1} + \sum \beta X_{it} + \lambda_i + \lambda_t + e_{it} \quad (1)$$

DM showing the debt maturity for the sample firm i and time t. X shows the number of independent variables in the equation. λ_i is the dummy variable which shows change over firm to firm and λ_t shows the time effect.

Results & Discussions

Variables	Observations	Mean	Std Dev	Mini	Max
DM	2240	0.29	0.19	0.00	0.81
Assets Maturity	2240	14.19	2.25	0.00	60.67
Firm Quality	2240	0.27	1.12	-39.00	31.27
Tax rate	2240	0.31	1.02	0.00	31
Size	2240	7.47	1.69	1.98	12.07
Growth	2240	0.21	0.12	-0.55	1.99

Table shows the mean value of the variables taken in the study. The mean values shows the average value of the debt maturity, assets maturity, firm quality etc. the table also mentioned the minimum value and maximum value of the variable which shows both extreme ends in the data set used for the data analysis.

Mean of variables (Sector wise)

Variables	Cement	Textile	Sugar	Power	Others
DM	0.39	0.31	0.19	0.29	0.29
Assets Maturity	12.01	11.33	13.98	11.22	14.02
Firm Quality	0.41	0.40	-0.29	0.10	0.44
Tax rate	0.20	0.19	0.66	0.20	0.22
Size	7.01	6.59	7.59	9.11	7.12
Growth	0.17	0.21	0.13	0.09	0.10

Table 2 shows the mean values of the respective variables for the different sectors taken in the study. The mean values for the different sectors were taken to know the level of debt maturity, assets maturity, firm quality etc. the mean values exhibits the ratio of debts using by the non-financial firms in Pakistani market.

Regression

DM	OLS		Fixed	
	Beta (t)	p-value	Beta (t)	p-value
Assets Maturity	0.0051 (2.13)	0.001	0.0021 (3.18)	0.000
Firm Quality	-0.0021 (0.18)	0.279	-0.0019 (-0.16)	0.231
Tax rate	-0.0019 (2.01)	0.043	-0.0023 (-3.17)	0.000
Size	0.031(3.19)	0.000	0.029 (2.01)	0.002
Growth	0.016 (5.90)	0.000	0.020 (1.18)	0.291

The table shows the findings taken from the regression model used in the study for checking the determinants of debt maturity. The results were based on both OLS and fixed effect model. The results reveal that assets maturity is having significant effect on the debt maturity while same significant result can be seen in the case of tax rate. The firm quality is showing insignificant effect on the debt maturity. The size and growth is having significant effect on the debt maturity. The findings of the study argued assets maturity is having significant effect on the debt maturity. The result reveals that selection of long and short term debt is a very critical decision taken by the finance manager. Shah (2007) argued that firms have different parameters which they examined before making their decision for the selection of debt. Different studies argued that the assets should be match with their debts as the firm should cover their debts with their assets, failing which they will face liquidity problem in future. The firm quality is having negative relationship with the debt maturity. Myers (1977) argued that the information asymmetry can also be the most significant factor the debt maturity. This means that the firm will prefer short term debts instruments when they are having higher risk or information asymmetry.

The tax rate is having significant effect on the debt maturity which argued that the tax rate can be involved in the selection of debt instrument. The study Miler (1977) argued that when the market is having higher taxes then they prefer to use debt instruments.

GMM

Variables	OLS Coeff(p)	Within group Coeff(p)	AH 2SLS Coeff(p)	GMM diff Coeff(p)	GMM sys Coeff(p)
DM _{t-1}	0.621(.00)	0.119(.00)	0.591(.00)	0.419(.00)	0.618(.00)
Assets Maturity	0.0021(.00)	0.0025(.00)	0.019(.41)	0.021(.12)	0.013(.00)
Firm Quality	-0.0019(.18)	0.0916(.17)	-0.0091(.26)	0.1084(.19)	0.0540(.29)
Tax rate	-0.0039(.00)	0.0017(.31)	-0.0216(.00)	-0.0018(.00)	-0.0067(.00)
Size	0.0077(.00)	0.0862(.00)	-0.0077(.00)	0.1284(.27)	0.0406(.00)
Growth	0.0628(.00)	0.0021(.00)	0.0401(.00)	0.0312(.10)	0.0404(.00)
No. of firms	224	224	224	224	224
No of Obs	2240	2240	2240	2240	2240
Wald (joint)	2278(7)	41.21(7)	6.79(9)	61.69(7)	511(10)
Wald (time)	11.87(3)	6.791	5.97(2)	10.14(3)	12.98(3)
Sargan test				46.79(37)	67.98(56)
Diff Sargan					0.29
AR (1)	-0.31	(4.01)	-5.97	-5.67	-7.17
AR (2)	0.39	-7.11	1.138	0.410	0.8800

Before estimating the GMM model, it is important that the endogeneity and exogeneity should be estimated for explanatory variables due to the fact that the valid instrument set is dependent on the association between the transformed error term (Shah, 2007). Following the model stated by Shah (2007), the table has included OLS, GMM within group, AH 2SLS, GMM difference and GMM system. The findings show that the debt maturity_{t-1} is having significant effect in whole categories. Assets maturity has been showing significant effect in OLS and within group while having insignificant effect in GMM difference. The study conducted by Morris (1976) argued that the firm opts to use the policy in which they match their debt maturity with their assets to avoid the liquidity problem in future. Failure in the debt and assets maturity will bear the risk of default or liquidity issues in future. According to Myers (1977) the matching of maturity for assets and debts significantly controls the agency problem between creditors and management. Hart (1994) argued that the matching the maturity of debts and assets help in controlling the risk and also the bankruptcy cost. Other studies Ozkan (2000), Korner (2007), Shah (2007) and Teruel and Solano (2010) have studied the maturity of assets and debt and concluded that the firms having higher assets maturity will have higher debt maturity. The findings for firm quality have been found that the insignificant results have been received in whole categories. The study of Mitchell (1991) argued that when there is higher information asymmetry then the firm will prefer to use short term debts. The study of Flannery (1986) shows that the longer debts are more sensitive to the firm value and they can be mismatch highly as compared to the short term debts. The study of Datta and Datta (2000) concluded a negative association among the firm's abnormal return and maturity of debts and same findings have been predicted by Flannery (1986). The findings of firm quality in the existing study are consistent with the study of Scherr and Hulburt (2001) who sees inverse relation between firm quality and debt maturity. The findings for tax rate are significant in OLS, GMM difference and GMM system while it is insignificant in within group. MM (1958) have examined the impact of tax on capital structure and argued in the perfect market and in the absence of tax there is no impact on the capital structure. This relates that the tax has no relation with the firm value. But later, new studies have been concluded that use of debts is related to the existence of taxes in the market (Miler, 1977). The market having higher taxes or double taxation policy like Pakistan, the investors will prefer to invest in the debts due to the higher income tax on the dividend and personal income. The higher debts usage means higher tax shield. Later on, the studies conducted by Lopez and Mestre (2011) and Fan et al., (2012) have argued that when the debt benefits are superior, the market will tend to use more debts. The findings of the study argued that the larger firms are having low level of information asymmetry and agency problems. Higher assets with the firm mean that the higher investment projects and thus having higher access to the long term debts (Shah, 2007). The study of Jalilvad and Harris (1984) argued that the smaller firms are having higher agency problems and they are more expose to risk and prefer to use short term debts.

4. Conclusion

The existing study has explored the determinants of debt maturity among the listed non-financial firms in Pakistan Stock Exchange. The study has included 10 years data from 2010 to 2019 for 224 non-financial firms. The study has taken dynamic models i.e. OLS, GMM etc for the estimation of determinants of debt maturity. The existing will contribute a significant portion in the literature after Shah (2007) for the debt maturity structure using GMM model. The study has explained different theories taken from the literature linked with the debt maturity. The different concepts have been explored in the context of debt maturity structure i.e. agency cost theory, liquidity risk theory, signaling theory, tax hypotheses and tax hypotheses. The findings of the study suggested that smaller firms are in favor of using more short term debts and as per the study of Shah (2007) no evidence was seen that the firm growing in size will use higher ratio of short term debts. The findings suggested that the size of the firm is positively related to debt maturity structure. The findings support the signaling hypotheses by confirming that larger firms always prefer to adopt short term debts by giving positive signals to the market. The tax hypotheses argued that when the market is having higher and growing tax rate then the use of debt instruments will be at peak.

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